

STRENGTHENING BEHAVIOR OF FEW-LAYERED GRAPHENE/ALUMINUM COMPOSITES

Seun Shin, and Donghyun Bae*

Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Yonsei University, Korea

Email: seun.shin@yonsei.ac.kr, web page: <http://mse.yonsei.ac.kr>

Keywords: Metal matrix composites (MMCs), Graphene, Load transfer,

ABSTRACT

Strengthening behaviour of composite containing discontinuous reinforcement is strongly related with load transfer at the reinforcement–matrix interface. Few-layer graphene (FLG) as a reinforcing agent and aluminum (Al) as a matrix are selected, respectively. By varying a volume fraction of the FLG, Al matrix composites were produced by a powder metallurgy method. Uniform dispersion and uniaxial alignment of FLG in the Al matrix are evidenced by high-resolution transmission electron microscope analysis. The composite with only an addition of 0.7 volume fraction of FLG exhibits ~440 MPa of tensile strength. To investigate strengthening behaviour of the composite containing discontinuous reinforcement, multi-walled carbon nanotube (MWCNT) and FLG reinforced Al matrix composites are compared. In terms of load transfer, surface area of the reinforcement is significantly important, although the reinforcements have a similar molecular structure, FLG has a 12.8 times larger specific surface area per volume more than MWCNT due to geometric difference. Therefore an increment of a yield stress versus a reinforcement volume fraction for FLG shows 3.5 times higher than that of MWCNT. Consequently, for both reinforcements, the composite strength proportionally increases with the specific surface area on the composite.

INTRODUCTION

Graphene is a single atomic layer of graphite with excellent mechanical properties, with the highest known intrinsic strength of 130 GPa and Young's modulus of 1 TPa [1-2]. Therefore, it has excellent potential as a reinforcing agent in composites owing to its 2-dimensional geometry and high mechanical properties. In order to transmit the excellent properties of graphene to composites, uniform dispersion and exfoliation is very important. Several processes have been introduced to exfoliate graphite to single or few layer graphene by mechanical and/or chemical methods [3-5]. However, both mechanical and chemical exfoliation methods do not well enough to use large-scale production or have environmental problem. Recently, solid phase techniques, combined with ball-milling processes, have enabled production of scalable quantities of carbon-base nano-materials by applying shear forces on pristine agglomerated particles [4-6]. Even though one has developed a scalable process to produce few-layer graphene (FLG), an additional technical hurdle is in the uniform dispersion of the graphene in the metal matrix, which has closely packed atomic structures. Hence, graphene/metal composites have been seldom investigated compared to polymer matrix composites, although the great strength and light weight features of graphene/metal composites are expected to lead to applications of such composites in the automotive and aerospace industries.

The primary objective of this work is to produce Al matrix composites with well-dispersed FLG using a scalable powder metallurgy approach. Here, we introduce a favorable route to produce centimeter-scale Al/FLG composites with excellent performances. This work also aims to examine tensile properties of the Al/FLG composite as a function of volume fraction of FLG, so as to compare the strengthening behavior of FLG with that of multi-walled carbon nanotube (MWCNT). Further, this work quantifies the effect of shape factor (i.e., tube versus sheet) and specific surface area of reinforcement on the composite strength.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Morphologies of ball-milled Al/FLG composite powders are shown in Figure 1. Exfoliated FLG sheets with sizes below 10 μm where FLG is marked by an arrow in Fig. 1a. Fig. 1b displays magnified images of rectangles in Fig. 1a, where FLG is thin enough to transmit the electron beam so the Al powder underneath the FLG can be seen.

Figure 1: SEM images of exfoliated graphene.

Figure 2 exhibits the powder morphology after attrition milling. FLG is not observed on the powder surface even in the magnified image. Hence, the FLG is supposed to be embedded and dispersed inside the Al powder.

Figure 2: SEM images of Al/FLG composite powder.

Figure 3 provides Raman spectra of the initial graphite powder, exfoliated graphite powder and Al/FLG composites with various volume fractions of FLG. Typical D-band (from defect and amorphous carbon), G-band (from graphite), and 2D band (shape of the second-order Raman bands) of graphitic carbons are detected at 1359, 1603, and 2727 cm^{-1} respectively [7,8], for the initial graphite powder. These bands shift to lower values (red-shift) as exfoliation proceeds, presumably because the surface of graphite powder might strongly interact with isopropyl alcohol, and the functionalized surface may generate a certain amount of in-plane internal stresses and weaker C-C bonds [9]. The peaks shift back toward their expected position after attrition and planetary milling with Al powder. As FLG is dispersed inside Al, it may not interact with other material any longer, and hence the

residual stresses could be released. The ratio between the intensities of the D and G bands, I_D/I_G , is considered to be the ratio of structural defects and domain size in graphitic materials [10]. The I_D/I_G ratio increases significantly after planetary milling with isopropyl alcohol and remains largely the same after attrition milling and hot-rolling processes. Therefore, FLG is thought to be damaged most during milling with isopropyl alcohol. The down-shifted 2D band, which is related to the crystalline graphitic structure, from 2727 cm^{-1} to 2678 cm^{-1} , arises from a reduction of the number of graphite layers during the ball milling processes [11]. For Al/FLG composites, the 2D band can be fitted with a sharp and symmetric peak, while that of graphite can be fitted with two peaks. It can be seen in Fig. 2 that the 2D band becomes sharper and shifted when the graphene thickness decreases [12].

Figure 3: Raman analysis of Al/FLG composite powder.

TEM images are shown in Figure 4 (FLGs are marked by an arrow). The mechanically exfoliated FLG, with sizes ranging from 50 to 200 nm, are observed to be dispersed piece by piece in the Al matrix. FLGs, aligned along the rolling direction are slightly wrinkled and folded with 100–200 nm in the long axis. The average thickness and layer number of graphene in the composite are statistically measured to be ~ 5 nm and ~ 5 layers, respectively. The average thickness of the composite is ~ 5 nm (standard deviation ~ 2 nm), while the number of layers of the graphene is ~ 5 layers (standard deviation ~ 2 nm).

Figure 4: TEM images of Al/FLG composite powder.

Figure 5 compares strengthening efficiency of FLG (solid squares, based on experimental data [13]) and MWCNT (open squares, obtained from [14]) in Al-based composites. An increase in strength with volume fraction of the reinforcements, calculated as $d\sigma_c/dV_r$, is closely related to load transfer from the matrix to the reinforcement. Interestingly, the linear fit of the slope, $d\sigma_c/dV_{graphene}$, is ~ 25.7 GPa while $d\sigma_c/dV_{CNT}$ is ~ 7.5 GPa. Despite the similar molecular structure and mechanical properties, FLG is found to be ~ 3.5 times more effective in strengthening aluminum as compared to MWCNT.

Figure 5: Variation of yield stress as a function of the volume fraction of reinforcements (FLG [13] and MWCNT [14]).

Table 1 : Schematic depiction of effective volume difference for various reinforcements.

	MWCNT	Graphene
Depiction	<p>Length (l): $1 \mu\text{m}^*$</p> <p>Diameter (d_f): 35 nm^*</p>	<p>Width (w): 150 nm^*</p> <p>Length (l): 100 nm^*</p> <p>Thickness (t): 5 nm^*</p>

Critical length (l_c , μm)	2	0.381
S / 1 ea	$\pi d_f l$	$2(w + t)l$
A / 1 ea	$\frac{\pi d_f^2}{4}$	wt
Volume / 1 ea ($\times 10^{-22} \text{ m}^3$)	9.62	0.75
Number of reinforcement/ Volume ($\times 10^{19} / \text{m}^3$)	1.01	13.3

Our calculation begins with the aforementioned force balance between the interfacial shear stress and reinforcement tensile stress for the case of composites containing MWCNT as [15]:

$$\tau_m (\pi d_f) dx = \left(\frac{\pi d_f^2}{4} \right) d\sigma_f \quad (1)$$

where τ_m is the shear strength of the matrix ($\sim 0.5\sigma_m$, σ_m is the tensile yield strength of the matrix), which is supposed to be the shear stress that the matrix transmits to the MWCNT, x is the axial distance from the tips of the MWCNT, d_f is the average diameter of MWCNT, and σ_f is the (position specific) tensile stress of the MWCNT. This expression can be modified for composites containing FLG as:

$$\tau_m \{2(w + t)\} dx = (wt) d\sigma_p \quad (2)$$

where w is the width of the FLG, t is the thickness of FLG, x is the distance from the end of the FLG, and σ_p is the (position specific) tensile stress of FLG. Both reinforcements are shorter than critical length, we can predict the theoretical composite strength can be expressed as:

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_r V_r \left(\frac{l}{2l_c} \right) + \sigma_m V_m \quad (3)$$

where V_r and V_m are the volume fraction of the reinforcements and the matrix, respectively. Applying this simplification to the reinforcements, the expression proposed for composite strength can be obtained from Eq. (3):

$$\sigma_c = V_r \left(\frac{S}{A} \right) \left(\frac{\tau_m}{2} \right) + \sigma_m V_m \quad (4)$$

Consequently, the calculated data using Eq. (4), which is a good correlation containing a quantitative estimate of the reinforcements and contact area based on force balance, exhibit good agreement with the experimental values.

Figure 6 shows variation in yield stress as a function of surface area per composite volume, where strengthening efficiency for two reinforcements is compared. The composite strength proportionally increases with the surface area per composite volume, and the increase is very similar for both reinforcements.

Figure 6: Variation of yield stress as a function of the volume fraction of reinforcements (FLG [13] and MWCNT [14]).

CONCLUSIONS

Al matrix composite containing FLG was successfully produced through a novel fabrication approach that combines mechanical milling and hot rolling. FLG was mechanically exfoliated using wet ball milling, and was then uniformly dispersed in the Al matrix using high energy ball milling. The strengths of the Al/FLG composites are significantly enhanced with the volume fraction of FLG. With an addition of only 0.7 vol% FLG, the composite exhibits 440 MPa of tensile strength, about two times higher than that of monolithic Al. Furthermore, the composites produced via favorable industrial routes using inexpensive graphite will increase a potential market opportunity of Al/FLG composites. On the other hand, with respect to the yield stress of MWCNT-reinforced Al matrix composites, FLG is a much more effective reinforcement because it has a larger surface area per unit volume. Our study highlighted that the specific surface area of the reinforcement can determine the strength of the composites.

REFERENCES

- [1] Lee C, Wei X, Kysar, JW, Hone J. Measurement of the elastic properties and intrinsic strength of monolayer graphene. *Science* **321**, 2008, pp. 385-388.
- [2] Martinez A, Fuse K, Yamashita S. Mechanical exfoliation of graphene for the passive mode-locking of fiber lasers. *Appl Phys Lett* **99**, 2011, pp.121107.
- [3] Hernandez Y, Nicolosi V, Lotya M, Blighe FM, Sun ZY, De S, et al. High-yield production of graphene by liquid-phase exfoliation of graphite. *Nat Nanotechnol* **3**, 2008, pp.563–8.
- [4] Zhao W, Fang M, Wu F, Wu H, Wang L, Chen G. Preparation of graphene by exfoliation of graphite using wet ball milling. *J Mater Chem.* **20**, 2010, pp.5817–9.
- [5] Zhao W, Wu F, Wu H, Chen G. Preparation of Colloidal dispersions of graphene sheets in organic solvents by using ball milling. *J Nanomaterials* 2010,528235.

- [6] Antisari MV, Montone A, Jovic N, Piscopiello E, Alvani C, Pilloni L. Low energy pure shear milling: a method for the preparation of graphite nano-sheets. *Scripta Mater* **55**,2006, pp. 1047–50.
- [7] Castiglioni C, Tommasini M, Zerbi G. Raman spectroscopy of polyconjugated molecules and materials: confinement effect in one and two dimensions. *Phil Trans R Soc Lond A* **362**, 2004,2425–59.
- [8] Kudin KN, Ozbas B, Schniepp HC, Prud'homme RK, Aksay IA, Car R. Raman Spectra of Graphite Oxide and Functionalized Graphene Sheets. *Nano Lett* **8**,2008,36–41.
- [9] Wang Z, Ciselli P, Peijs T. The extraordinary reinforcing efficiency of single-walled carbon nanotubes in oriented poly(vinyl alcohol) tapes. *Nanotechnology* 2007;18:455709.
- [10] Antunes EF, Lobo AO, Corat EJ, Trava-Airoldi VJ, Martin AA, Veríssimo C. Comparative study of first- and second-order Raman spectra of MWCNT at visible and infrared laser excitation. *Carbon* 2006;44(11):2202–11.

- [11] Ferrari AC, Meyer JC, Scardaci V, Casiraghi C, Lazzeri M, Mauri F et al. Raman spectrum of graphene and graphene layers. *Phys Rev Lett* **97**,2006,187401.
- [12] Li D, Zhan D, Yan J, Sun CL, Li ZW, Ni ZH et al. Thickness and stacking geometry effects on high frequency overtone and combination Raman modes of graphene. *J Raman Spectrosc* **44**,2013,86–91.
- [13] Shin SE, Choi HJ, Shin JH, Bae DH. Strengthening behavior of few-layered graphene/aluminum composites. *Carbon* **82**, 2015, 143–51.
- [14] Choi HJ, Shin JH, Bae DH. Grain size effect on the strengthening behavior of aluminum-based composites containing multi-walled carbon nanotubes. *Compo Sci Technol* **71**, 2011,1699–1705.
- [15] Courtney TH. Mechanical behavior of materials. 2nd ed. Singapore: McGraw-Hill Book Co; 2000.